

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP2 – Outcome Driven Healthcare

D2.1 Selected priority therapeutic areas

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	D2.1 – Selected priority therapeutic areas		
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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	05 March 2019	First Draft
V0.2	21 March 2019	Second draft
V1.0	8 May 2019	Third draft
V2.0	23 May 2019	Final Version for consortium review
V2.0	11 Jun 2019	Final version for submission

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

WP2 will extend the OMOP-CDM and vocabularies to include all ICHOM standard sets. A standard set encompasses standardised outcomes, measurement tools, time points and risk adjustment factors for a given condition. Currently, 28 standard sets are available (www.ichom.org).

The work in WP2 will need to use only a small number of the standard sets for the development of dashboards, and the work to extend the vocabularies will take time. Therefore, priority must be given to initiate this work to start with the most relevant/highest priority standard sets. The following considerations for selecting the highest priority ICHOM standard sets were considered:

- Can the standard set be used as part of EHDEN research activities that are either ongoing or planned for years 1 and 2 of the project?
- Which conditions are indicated as high priority by Consortium members (through a ranking exercise)?
- What standard sets overlap with current or future BD4BO projects?

After a shortlisting exercise, EHDEN partners were invited to nominate their priority standard sets. This resulted in the following two ICHOM standard sets to be selected: inflammatory arthritis and prostate cancer (locally and advanced). However, all the sets will be dealt with during the project.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The main objective of WP2 is to enable the transition towards outcomes-driven healthcare systems in Europe. This can only be achieved if the EHDEN framework can be used in the context of regulatory approval, health technology assessment (HTA), and for payer purposes. As the EHDEN project is using the OMOP-CDM to build a federated network of data sources standardised to a common data model, WP2 will test whether the OMOP-CDM can be used for regulatory, HTA and payer activities.

WP2 also will extend the OMOP-CDM and vocabularies to include the ICHOM standard set. A standard set encompasses standardised outcomes, measurement tools, time points and risk adjustment factors for a given condition. ICHOM standard sets are developed through consensus and the process involves experts and patient representatives, to ensure the standard sets include those outcomes most relevant to patients. Currently, 28 standard sets are available (www.ichom.org). More information about the standard sets, and the outcomes that are included in each set, can be found on the ICHOM website.

However, not all standard sets will be equally relevant for measuring outcomes of drugs (a key focus of regulatory, HTA and payer activities). The following considerations for selecting the highest priority ICHOM standard sets will be considered:

- Can the standard set be used as part of EHDEN research activities that are either ongoing or planned for years 1 and 2 of the project?
- Which conditions are indicated as high priority by Consortium members (through a ranking exercise?)
- What standard sets overlap with current or future BD4BO projects?

2. METHODS

The currently available ICHOM standard sets cover the following conditions:

1. Heart failure
2. Coronary artery disease
3. Atrial fibrillation
4. Hypertension in low- and middle-income countries
5. Stroke
6. Parkinson's disease
7. Colorectal cancer
8. Breast cancer
9. Localised prostate cancer
10. Advanced prostate cancer
11. Lung cancer
12. Diabetes
13. Inflammatory arthritis
14. Inflammatory bowel disease
15. Overactive bladder
16. Chronic kidney disease
17. Pregnancy and childbirth
18. Paediatric facial palsy
19. Congenital upper limb abnormalities
20. Craniofacial microsomia
21. Cleft lip and palate
22. Older person
23. Dementia

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24. Depression and anxiety
25. Hip and knee osteoarthritis
26. Low back pain
27. Macular degeneration
28. Cataracts

The current BD4BO portfolio has projects on the following disease areas:

- Haematological malignancies (HARMONY)
- Prostate cancer (PIONEER)
- Alzheimer’s disease (ROADMAP)
- Cardiovascular disease (BigData@Heart)

An initial short-listing exercise by WP2 members identified the following shortlist of standard sets:

Overlap with current or planned BD4BO projects:

1. Advanced prostate cancer
2. Localised prostate cancer
3. Coronary artery disease
4. Dementia
5. Heart failure

Overlap with currently ongoing and planned research in EHDEN use cases:

1. Diabetes
2. Inflammatory arthritis
3. Colorectal cancer
4. Breast cancer
5. Parkinson’s disease
6. Lung cancer

We needed to select two standard sets that will be prioritised to initiate the process of extending the OMOP-CDM vocabularies, that will then be scaled up to the other standard sets. the priority sets will also be used to develop the dashboards that are planned for deliverable [D2.4]. We posted the short list on the EHDEN forum and invited all Consortium members to select their preferred standard sets.

3. RESULTS

We posted the short list on the EHDEN Forum and invited all partners to indicate their preferred standard sets. Seven EHDEN consortium partners replied and indicated their preferred set (Figure 1). Inflammatory arthritis received the most votes (4 out of 7 respondents selected this standard set), followed by colorectal cancer and prostate cancer (3 votes each).

4. DISCUSSION

The objective of D2.1 was to select two ICHOM standard sets to prioritise for being added to the OMOP-CDM vocabularies first (D2.2; D2.3), and to subsequently be used to drive the dashboards development under D2.4. The shortlisting process presented 11 ICHOM standard sets to all EHDEN partners and three standard sets received most votes: Inflammatory arthritis, colorectal cancer, and prostate cancer. As the inflammatory arthritis standard set received most votes from EHDEN partners, this standard set was selected as a priority. Two standard sets received 3 votes each, but prostate cancer is also a focus of the BD4BO project PIONEER. Therefore, the second standard set to be selected as a priority disease area is the prostate cancer standard (localised and advanced).

5. CONCLUSION

The two priority disease areas selected by EHDEN are **prostate cancer** and **inflammatory arthritis**. These ICHOM standards will therefore be added to the OMOP-CDM first and will be used for the development of the relevant dashboards under D2.4 (planned for M24). After the first sets are added, the rest of the standard sets will also be added to the vocabularies. If the experience with the first two sets will lead to the conclusion that adding the rest of the standard sets will take considerable amount of time, another prioritisation exercise might be warranted. However, it is expected that it will not be a time-consuming exercise.